

The Governance and Accountability of Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) in India

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Abstract:

NGOs are both praised and criticized in the current reformulations of governance for development. Although they are expected to take the position of the state in a number of capacities and endeavors, there are growing doubts about their ability, legitimacy, and credibility to do so. Growth has increased the sector's prominence, which has drawn critical attention from the policy and research communities—particularly with regard to issues of NGOs' governance. NGOs (non-governmental organizations) deal with trust and accountability challenges. Concerns about improving NGOs' efficacy and performance as well as holding them more accountable for the funding they get are becoming more prevalent. The trust and credibility difficulties facing non-governmental organizations, along with a few elements that could enhance their efficacy, performance, and credibility. Corporate-NGO partnerships are sometimes brief collaborations with very specific goals, such as events, campaigns, programs, or initiatives where the primary business of the corporate organization and the NGO's field of expertise overlap.

Keyword: Accountability, Transparency, Responsibility Financial resources, NGO movements, Efficiency problems of NGOs

Introduction:

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) are becoming an unstoppable force in the world. The voluntary sector, sometimes referred to as the non-governmental sector, is expanding in proportion to its involvement in developmental initiatives. Most places in the universe today acknowledge and embrace its significance in the field of human growth. In essence, non-governmental organizations, also known as voluntary organizations, are for-profit organizations founded with the intention of helping the underprivileged, marginalized, poor, downtrodden, and needy. They are also more accessible to the target groups, have flexible administrative structures, make decisions quickly, take prompt action, and help the people become self-sufficient while guaranteeing their full involvement in the process of development. Lester Salamon recently completed a major multi-nation study and found that NGOs are a huge economic and social force. The study clearly highlighted the rapid rise of NGOs. The author observes that the emergence of the non-profit sector on a worldwide scale could be deemed just as significant a development of the late 20th century as the nation-state's formation was in the earlier 19th century. The study team discovered a strikingly wide range of non-profit activity in nearly every location they studied.

The research, which encompasses nations such as France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, the UK, the US, Brazil, Ghana, and India, bolsters the belief that the industry is unquestionably progressing quickly across numerous domains of human endeavor. According to the report, has grown to be a significant employer, providing jobs for seven million Americans, 1.4 million Japanese, and almost a million individuals in France, Germany,

and the UK put together. One in every eleven workers in these nations holds a service-related job, making up an average of 3.4 percent of the labor force. Additionally, it is discovered that the industry spends enormous quantities, with an average of 3.5 percent and variances between 1.2 and 6.3 percent of GDP in Hungary and the US.

It appears that the last 20 years have seen particularly remarkable expansion in the voluntary sector. Over the years, there has been a noticeable increase in the presence of NGOs, particularly those working on development projects. In actuality, NGOs' role in development is now essential. It is estimated that NGOs currently handle around 10% of the \$8 billion in public development aid provided globally. That being said, nothing has changed in India. If the number of NGOs growing is any guide, the industry is growing daily. According to a conservative estimate, there are more than 0.2 million NGOs worldwide. Only those registered for certification to receive foreign assistance are included in this number; trade unions, schools, and hospitals are not included.

INDIA'S NGOs:

Voluntary action has a very long history. "Volunteerism operated freely and exclusively in the fields of education, medicine, cultural promotion, and even acted as succour in crises like droughts, floods, epidemics, and foreign invasions" (Inamdar, 1987). This is according to Inamdar.

Early in the 19th century, underprivileged and weaker segments of society received services from volunteer organizations. The majority of the work was done in the areas of social reform and religion. The individuals who dedicatedly worked to remove caste restrictions, improve widows' and women's education conditions, and help orphans and destitute women included Raja Rammohan Roy

(1772–1833), Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar (1820–1891), Sasi Pada Banarjee (1842–1925), Keshab Chandra Sen (1838–1884), Swami Dayanand Saraswati (1824–1883), Swami Vivekanand (1863–1902), Mahatma Phule (1827–1888), Pandit Ramabai (1858–1922), Maharshi Karve (1858–1962), Sir Sayyed Ahmed Khan (1817–1898), and Behramji Malbari (1853–1912).

Christian missionaries also pioneered work in the subject of social welfare in the second half of the 1800s. Along with enhancing their living conditions and health, they also became interested in educating women, indigenous people, and others. In the early 20th century, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) worked in a variety of sectors, including health, education, and labor welfare, in addition to providing relief and rehabilitation efforts during natural disasters like earthquakes, floods, and famines.

Chowdhry claims that social workers who had served under Gandhi's leadership gave India's leadership after independence. In actuality, they were the ones who initiated the volunteer action movement in the areas of health, education, social welfare, adult education, rural development, etc., in both urban and rural areas (1987). In addition to encouraging nonprofits to launch social welfare initiatives under the grant-in-aid program and establishing independent entities like the Central Social Welfare Board and Indian Council of Social Welfare, the government implemented welfare programs under a number of plans and regulations.

A number of establishments, including those founded by Christian missionaries, Indian benefactors, the Ramakrishna Mission, and Mahatma Gandhi and the wives of officers with the backing of the British Government, remained operational. Notwithstanding the fact that nationwide organizations such as the Harijan Sevak Sangh, YMCA, YWCA, and Indian Red Cross Society were operational. Around this period, a number of nationwide voluntary organizations were established, including the Association of Social Health, the Kasturba Gandhi National Memorial Trust, the Indian Council of Child Welfare, and the Youth Hostel Association (1999).

The second half of the 1970s saw a growth in community organizations. Additionally, a radical trend developed, with social action organizations adopting the stance that poverty is a structural issue that needs to be actively addressed by the rural poor's mobilization. With generous foreign funding, social action groups mushroomed in the late 1970s and early 1980s, taking over as the predominant form of non-governmental organization (NGO) in several states, most notably Tamil Nadu and Bihar, in stark contrast to the program-focused approaches that had become popular since the 1960s.

Within the NGO movement, another trend began to emerge in the mid-1980s, stressing the value of a professional approach built on strong administration, planning, and coordination. In the 1980s, public involvement in development was very noticeable. The establishment of resource organizations, which deal directly with the underprivileged and offer other NGOs support services like training, assessment, and documentation, was a parallel growth (Umukoro, 2009).

To better the situation in rural areas, the Council for Advancement of Rural Technologies (CART) was established in 1983. The Council for the Advancement of People's Action and Rural Technology (CAPART) was established in 1986 through the merger of CART and People Action for Development in India (PADI). The organization's primary goals were to create jobs, generate income, develop community assets, and meet basic needs like housing and drinking water (2000). The empowerment concept gained popularity in the 1990s. NGOs started engaging in campaigning and lobbying to counter the threats and challenges posed by macro forces to the marginalized and impoverished people living in rural areas. NGOs' operations have brought them into closer touch with the public as a result of their increased size and impact.

NGOs were further acknowledged by the Eighth Plan, which also encouraged them to take part in cutting-edge initiatives like the watershed development project under the DPAP and Agro Climatic Regional Planning (ACRP). The Ninth Plan called for NGOs to be involved from the outset of planning. The main focus of the SGSY program, which was introduced in 1999 and combined other rural development schemes like JRY and IRDP, is still group lending. NGOs are heavily influencing SHGs because they have been at the forefront of promoting SHGs.

NGOs IN INDIA:

voluntary action is very ancient. According to Inamdar, "During ancient and medieval times, voluntarism operated freely and exclusively in the fields of education, medicine, cultural promotion and even acted as succour in crises like droughts, floods, epidemics and foreign invasions" (1987).

In the early years of 19th century, voluntary agencies provided services to the under-privileged and weaker sections of the society. The areas of operation were largely in the fields of religion and social reforms. Raja Rammohan Roy (1772 -1833), Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar (1820-1891), Sasi Pada Banarjee (1842-1925), Keshab Chandra Sen (1838-1884), Swami Dayanand Saraswati (1824-1883), Swami Vivekanand (1863- 1902), Mahatma phule (1827-1888), Pandit Ramabai (1858-1922), Maharshi Karve (1858-1962), Sir Sayyed Ahmed

Khan (1817-1898), Behramji Malbari (1853-1912) were the people who worked with dedication towards removal of caste restrictions, improving conditions of widows, women education, orphans and destitute women etc.,

In the latter part of 19th century, Christian Missionaries also did pioneer work in the field of social welfare. They also took interest in spreading education among women, tribals, and others, and in improving their health and living conditions. In the early decades of 20th century, besides relief and rehabilitation programmes in times of natural calamities like earthquakes, floods and famines, NGOs were also engaged in various fields like education, health and labour welfare.

According to Chowdhry, "After Independence, leadership in India was provided by social workers who had worked under the leadership of Gandhi. As a matter fact, they were the ones who started the movement of voluntary action, both in urban and rural areas in the fields of health, education, social welfare, adult education, rural development etc.," (1987). The government undertook welfare schemes under various plans and policies, besides encouraging voluntary organizations to undertake social welfare programmes under the grant-in-aid programme and set up autonomous bodies like Central Social Welfare Board, Indian Council of Social Welfare etc.,

Some of the institutions started by Mahatma Gandhi and by the wives of the officers with the support of the British Government and those started by the Indian philanthropists, Christian Missionaries, Ramakrishna Mission etc, continued to function. Although national organizations like Indian Red Cross Society, Young Men's Christian Association (YMCA), Young Women's Christian Association (YWCA), Harijan Sevak Sangh etc, were functioning. It was around this time that several all-India level voluntary organizations such as Kasturba Gandhi National Memorial Trust, Indian Council of Child Welfare, Youth Hostel Association, Association of Social Health etc, were set up (1999).

During the latter half of the 1970s, community organizations gained momentum. Also, a radical trend emerged, with social action groups taking the view that poverty is a structural phenomenon which had to be tackled head-on through the active mobilization of the rural poor. With liberal foreign funding, social action groups proliferated throughout the late 1970s and early 1980s and established themselves as the dominant type of NGO in some states, notably Tamil Nadu and Bihar in sharp contrast to the programme-focused approaches which had found favour from the 1960s.

From the mid-1980s, a further trend emerged within the NGO movement, emphasizing the importance of professional approach based on sound management, planning and co-ordination. People's participation in development was much pronounced in 1980s. A parallel development was the creation of resource agencies which work directly with the poor and also provide support services to other NGOs in the form of training, evaluation and documentation (Umukoro, 2009).

In the year 1983 a new organization called Council for Advancement of Rural Technologies (CART) was set up to improve conditions in rural areas. In 1986, CART was merged with People Action for Development in India (PADI) to form Council for the Advancement of People's Action and Rural Technology (CAPART) and its main thrust was in the areas of employment, income generation, creation of community assets and fulfilment of basic needs like housing and drinking water (2000). In 1990s empowerment approach gained momentum. NGOs began to perform advocacy and lobbying in order to meet the challenges and threats of macro forces towards the rural poor and marginalized. As NGOs have grown in size and influence, their activities have brought them into closer contact with the Government. The NGOs are recognized by the government in rural reconstruction work. They received explicit recognition from the government in the latter half of 1980s. The Seventh Five Year Plan (1986-1990) emphasized the involvement of voluntary agencies in various proposed projects.

The Eighth Plan further gave credit to NGOs and encouraged them to participate in the innovative projects like Agro Climatic Regional Planning (ACRP), the watershed development project under DPAP etc. The Ninth Plan envisaged involving NGOs right from the planning process. In 1999 the SGSY scheme had been launched merging various Rural Development Schemes like IRDP, JRY etc., Group-lending remains the major thrust. As NGOs have done pioneering work in SHG promotion, they are being extensively involved in influencing the SHGs.

Problems Faced by NGOs In India:

The following are some of the main issues that NGOs in India are dealing with: RASS, Rural Reconstruction Society (RRS), Social Activities for Rural Development Society (SARDS), Community Action for Literacy and Livelihood (CALL), ASSIST, Rural Aid Service Organization (RASO), Society for National Integration through Rural Development (SNIRD), Rural Development Society (RDS), Rural and Urban Development Society, etc.

Lacking Funds for Programmes:

Lack of funding is a problem for the majority of NGOs in India. The government does not withhold aid in full or postpone approving funding for a number of initiatives. NGOs are not

always able to manage the matching contributions required of them, which prevents them from receiving the grants. Charity in the minds and emotions of people today is not as strong as it was in ancient societies. This was another area where NGOs' finances were stagnant.

Programmes Conducting Efficiency:

The state and caliber of services provided by any organization are determined by the leadership abilities of its leaders in non-governmental organizations. In this context, "Leadership for the sake of Leadership," or particularly committed leadership, is a crucial determining element. Unfortunately, in the post-independence era, NGOs faced a leadership vacuum as the leaders who had pioneered voluntary action and worked for it with a spirit of devotion and dedication chose to enter politics in order to find positions in legislatures and parliament. There are some assumptions that older people hold the majority of the leadership positions. The authoritarian manner in which these elderly individuals conduct themselves irritates younger individuals who represent fresh concepts, bold endeavours.

Deficiency of Social Work Professionals:

The professional skills of an organization's leaders in non-governmental organizations determine the condition and quality of services the organization offers. "Social work professional for the sake of Leadership," or more specifically, devoted leadership, is an important deciding factor in this situation. Unfortunately, the leaders of NGOs who had pioneered voluntary action and worked for it with a spirit of devotion and dedication chose to embrace politics in order to gain jobs in legislatures and parliament, leaving NGOs with a leadership vacuum in the post-independence era. Some people assume that the majority of leadership roles are held by older individuals. Younger people who represent new ideas, daring initiatives, and ingenuity but are not as old as these older people disturb me with their authoritarian demeanor.

Fund Divert or Misuse:

It is the matter of fact that some unscrupulous elements have made fortunes by floating NGOs for their personnel gains and managing grants from the government. It is a common experience that there have been serious charges of misuse and misappropriation of funds received as grant-in-aid form the government, foreign donors and raised through their own resources by the most of the NGOs. These NGOs may reflect its image to other NGOs who are working with dedication and commitment.

Lack of Coordination among Staff and Public Participation:

In non-governmental organizations, the state and caliber of services provided are determined

by the leadership abilities of the organization's leaders. In this case, "leadership for the sake of leadership," or more precisely, committed leadership, is a crucial differentiator. Unfortunately, in order to get positions in legislatures and parliament, the leaders of NGOs who had pioneered voluntary action and worked for it with a spirit of commitment and dedication chose to enter politics, leaving NGOs in need of leadership throughout the post-independence era. Some people believe that elderly people occupy the bulk of leadership positions. I find the authoritarian manner of younger individuals, who are not as old as these older people but symbolize bold ideas, inventiveness, and daring endeavors, to be unsettling.

Lack of Volunteerism/Social work among Youth:

The fundamental quality of an NGO is voluntarism. While volunteering was once a popular professional path for young people, it appears that this excitement has now waned. The amount of volunteerism is decreasing daily and becoming more and more professionalized. Even recent social work graduates are eager in pursuing careers in professionalism. As a result, NGOs struggle to find effective volunteers.

Time-bound and goal-oriented programs:

It has been noted that the government or donor endorsing the grant would present the NGO with time-bound and goal-oriented programs. These NGOs will require time, but the services they provide are of high caliber. As a result, the quality of the services declines and falls short of expectations.

Area of Interest:

Occasionally, an NGO will favor the donor's area of interest when it comes to welfare initiatives that go beyond his own preferences or involve multiple programs. Additionally, this causes the quality of services provided by that particular program to decline.

Suggestions:

The following are the suggested remedies to the problems of the NGOs in India.

1. The Indian government must approve more funding to NGOs and loosen the restrictions on grants-in-aid. In addition, the government ought to form committees or commissions of inquiry to double verify any misappropriation of funding by non-governmental organizations. Committee members are required to oversee and occasionally monitor the work of non-governmental organizations. Investigative measures like this could be the result of personnel or political vendettas.
2. Recent college, university, and school graduates must host public seminars, meetings, symposiums, and other events. They must also use the local media to promote volunteerism, highlight its value, highlight the accomplishments of NGOs, and inspire others to get involved.

3. In order to cultivate leadership in the next generation of leaders, the Indian government must incorporate the success stories of great leaders, along with their leadership attributes such as voluntarism, dedication, and commitment to social work, into the curricula of social work departments and the school syllabus. Young people's fresh perspectives, initiative, and inventiveness must aid in their development as outstanding leaders.

Conclusion:

NGOs are the ones who genuinely want to help the underprivileged and neglected segments of society. These kinds of devoted, committed, and committed organizations are necessary for the growth of our emerging nation. Therefore, in addition to the fact that these organizations' services are clearly praiseworthy in helping to uplift the rural poor, the government, leaders, funders, politicians, and the general public should support these groups and assist them in solving their problems at the grassroots level.

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